

The Oceans Heat Source Allocation

Bruce Williams*
Gillette, Wyoming, USA

Abstract

Williams[1] correlated the North Magnetic Dip Pole [NMDP] motion to the globe's High Geothermal Flux Activity [HGFA] of Viterito[2] with an r^2 value of 87.4 %. Based on this tight a correlation of determination a model was built to solve for the best solution of the sums of NMDP heat as a proxy for HGFA, Solar Irradiation [SIrr] heat and CO₂ heat to compute the Sea Surface Temperature [SST] in order to separate and determine the percentage of heat supplied by CO₂, HGFA, and SIrr. SST is used because all the sources and feedback's will be heating the sea surface directly. The results produced a correlation r^2 value of 79.61 %. Of the total heat added during the study period of 1880 to 1975 inclusive it is shown that 51 % of the heat increase was due to the HGFA heat addition to the oceans, 30 % was from increased CO₂, and 19 % was from SIrr; indicating that CO₂ is not the lone temperature driver nor is it the primary temperature driver at the present conditions of our climate with a certainty of ≈ 80 %.

Keywords: Seismic activity; Geothermal forcing; Magnetic Poles; Climate Change; CO₂; Solar Irradiance

Introduction

The present model [3] for the Earth's energy balance is presented simplistically as show in the picture below:

Presently the majority of the energy added to the earth's surface, including the sea, is attributed to the addition of CO₂ to the atmosphere and small changes in SIrr due to Solar and Orbital changes acting as the driving force for the condensables feedback, primarily water. All research so far is based on this concept[4]. As with any complex highly coupled random system, the collected data which has no hard basis, such as net absorbed, albedo, etc. is calculated based on the other values which themselves have had adjustments made to them. All these adjustments and estimates which make up the corrections to match the assumed model can introduce compound errors which may become large enough to mask unknowns which are significant. When Viterito[2] studied the interaction between the temperature of the globe and seismic data to address a point of difference within the scientific community as to assigning the proper percentages of energy change to the known factors that add heat to the globe he may have uncovered an unknown with a significant affect. The prior work done by Viterito[2] covered only a short period of time and only the effects of a single event, which may be an anomaly in itself. To address this question of long term validity and thus applicability, a much longer period would have to be analyzed to determine if the fundamental question of the HGFA activity affecting the temperature of the earth

holds true.

This paper looks at the long term, 1880 thru 1975, relationship between the three predictors consisting of the geological activity proxy, NMDP motion, the change in SIrr and atmospheric CO₂ summed to produce a Calculated SST [CSST] relative to the as Measured SST [MSST]. MSST was chosen because all three predictors add energy the sea surface directly with no significant dispersants.

There being 4 variables and only 1 equation, of the form

$$\text{NMDP}^{\circ}\text{C} + \text{CO}_2^{\circ}\text{C} + \text{SIrr}^{\circ}\text{C} + \text{Unknown}^{\circ}\text{C} = \text{MSST}$$

there is no way to create a simple equation to generate a true physical result. Since the MSST we are trying to describe is the momentum of atoms, something we call temperature, we must ensure that our results test that the three predictors follow five criteria.

1. The overall CSST result must correlate well with the overall MSST characteristics or we must say that we don't even know the major predictors involved. This will be referred to as End to End Correlation

2. Over an extended period of time as the MSST increases energy our CSST must produce an increase in the energy it calculates. And, conversely as the MSST energy decreases so must the energy the CSST calculates. If this does not hold true then we have an improper physical solution even if the overall mathematical solution shows good. To do this the slope direction of the CSST value versus the slope direction of the MSST is compared for each turning point in the MSST value. This will be referred to as the Timed Correlation.

3. The time weighted average of all Timed Correlation's must not be less than the End to End correlation under the fact that we must follow MSST better.

4. The CSST values must not be offset significantly from the MSST values.

5. The final criterion, realizing that the MSST does not instantaneously respond to applied energy because of its large volume we must make sure that each energy source has a time delay.

By eliminating any solutions which violate criteria 2 and 5, the result with the highest product of criteria 1, 3 and 4 will give us the physically best solution to the question of the proper energy sources.

*Corresponding author: Bruce Williams, Gillette, Wyoming-82718, USA, Tel: [REDACTED]; E-mail bbwilliams@bresnan.net

Received November 29, 2018; Accepted December 13, 2018; Published NA

Citation: [REDACTED]

Copyright: © 2018 Williams B. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Base Value

A 0°C base is used because the CO₂ temperature rise is base zero at the minimum CO₂ reading in each particular CO₂ offset data set.

North Magnetic Dip Pole Motion {NMDP}

The position of the NMDP was retrieved from NOAA[5] geomagnetic data.

Using the latitude and longitude values, the distance between each years position was calculated using first order true spherical distance calculations. From these values the rate of change for the pole was calculated on a yearly basis using the equation:

$$Km = \left(A \cos(\sin(Lat_1)\sin(Lat_2) + \cos(Lng_1)\cos(Lng_2 - Lng_1)) * \frac{180}{\pi} * 60 \right) * \quad (01)$$

Where:

Km = Kilometers moved from the previous years location.

Lat_1 = Previous years Latitude in radians.

Lng_1 = Previous years Longitude in radians.

Lat_2 = This years Latitude in radians.

Lng_2 = This years Longitude in radians.

Each iteration of NMDP its offset was decremented by 1 year to find its delay period.

Measured Sea Surface Temperature {MSST}

The MSST values were retrieved from the Met Office of the UK[6]. The monthly values were averaged for each year from 1874 to 1975.

MSST values were then adjusted using the equation:

$$MSST_i = MSST_o - MSST_{min} \quad (02)$$

Where:

$MSST_i$ = This years Measured SST deviation from low.

$MSST_o$ = This years Measured SST original reading.

$MSST_{min}$ = Measured SST lowest value in its data set.

To give us the change in temperature.

This value was never adjusted and is a series of constant points for the model.

This resulted in an MSST upper value of 0.723°C and a lower value of 0°C

CO₂

CO₂ data was taken from the NASA Giss site for the period 1874 to 1959[7] and from NOAA's Mauna Loa values from 1960 to present[8].

CO₂ values were convert by selecting an assumed °C rise for a doubling of CO₂ (2°C in the final runs) and then using the equation:

$$^{\circ}C_{ThisReading} = \left(\frac{\ln\left(\frac{CO_{2Raw}}{CO_{2Low}}\right)}{\ln(2)} \right) * ^{\circ}C_{Expected} \quad (03)$$

Where:

$^{\circ}C_{ThisReading}$ is this particular °C change caused by the CO₂ reading.

CO_{2Raw} is this particular CO₂ reading in ppm in that particular offset time periods data set.

CO_{2Low} is the lowest CO₂ ppm reading in that particular time periods data set.

$^{\circ}C_{Expected}$ is the expected °C rise for a doubling of CO₂.

The CO₂°C to be added to get CSST is not normalized to the MSST value since it is already a base 0°C temperature and it is a rise defined by the presently accepted model.

This °C value is then changed during a full run by a multiplication factor from 0.1 to 1 in 0.05 increments. The particular multiplier is included in the data output.

Each iteration of CO₂ its offset was decremented by 1 year to find its delay period.

Total Solar Irradiance {SIrr}

SIrr data was from the University of Colorado at Boulder, the TIM_TSI Reconstruction[9] of total solar irradiance from 1887 to 1975.

The only conditioning for SIrr data was normalizing using Eq (04).

Each iteration of SIrr its offset was decremented by 1 year to find its delay period.

Normalization

For each test, the NMDP and SIrr values were normalized to 0 to 0.723°C over the years in their respective offset data sets.

The equation used was:

$$^{\circ}C_N = MSST_{min} + \left(\frac{D - D_{min}}{D_{dif}} \right) * MSST_{dif} \quad (04)$$

Where:

$^{\circ}C_N$ = the normalized result in °C.

D = the particular raw data reading in that particular offset data set.

D_{min} = the minimum data value in that particular offset data set.

D_{dif} = the difference between the maximum and minimum data values in that particular data set.

$MSST_{min}$ = the minimum Measured SST value (0).

$MSST_{dif}$ = the difference between the maximum and minimum Measured SST values in its data set (0.723).

This then gives us a °C change *if* this would be the only factor and 100% efficient and responsive.

Criteria 1 & 3 calculations

Since there was only one variable (CSST) and one known quantity (MSST) a Pearson Correlation was used to determine both the End to End Correlation as well as the individual Timed Correlation values. The equation used was:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=Syr}^{Eyr} ((x_i - M_x) * (y_i - M_y))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=Syr}^{Eyr} (x_i - M_x)^2 * \sum_{i=Syr}^{Eyr} (y_i - M_y)^2}} \quad (05)$$

Where:

x_i = MSST Deviation at point i

y_i = CSST Deviation at point i

M_x = Mean of the MSST Deviation

M_y = Mean of the CSST Deviation

Syr = Start Year

Eyr = End Year

Criterion 2 calculations

The predictors must also produce a result that has increases and decreases, over a period of time, in CSST that do not oppose the MSST increases and decreases.

To calculate these values one must first determine the points where the MSST temperature changes slope. To do that we selected the break point times as 1895, 1912, and 1945 based on the MSST data. Graph 1 shows the MSST graph and the MSST linear regression lines overlaid for each break point:

The 1895 split is more apparent in the data than in the graph. From 1880 to 1894 the MSST data is either flat or decreasing, depending on how it is visually interpreted. From 1895 to 1911 the MSST is obviously decreasing, so 1895 was taken

as a break point. The other two break points are obvious even to the eye.

Graph 1 MSST and Linear Trend Lines

The linear regression equation used to calculate all values is:

$$B1 = \frac{\sum_{i=s}^{s+n} (x_i * y_i) - \frac{\sum_{i=s}^{s+n} (y_i) * \sum_{i=s}^{s+n} (x_i)}{n}}{\sum_{i=s}^{s+n} (x_i - M_x)^2} \quad (06)$$

for the B1 value (slope)

Where:

x_i = data point x axis value.

y_i = data point y axis value.

M_x = Median x axis value.

n = total number of data points.

The B0 (intercept) is calculated as:

$$B0 = M_y - B1 * M_x \quad (07)$$

Where:

M_y = Median y value for this set of data points.

$B1$ = the slope of the line.

M_x = Median x value for this set of data points.

The start y points are calculated as:

$$y_s = B0 + B1 * x_s \quad (08)$$

The end y points are calculated as:

$$y_e = B0 + B1 * x_e \quad (09)$$

Where:

x_s = start point x value.

x_e = end point x value. (10)

And the angle the line is at is calculated:

$$\alpha = \text{Atan} \left(\frac{y_e - y_s}{\text{Years}} \right) \quad (10)$$

Criterion 4 calculations

The requirement that the CSST values must not be offset significantly from the MSST values is detected by determining the % that the CSST error is of the MSST mean. The necessity of this is because Correlations do not check for offset, just similarity. Take for example the above graph of MSST vs MSST+0.5.

The correlation here will be 100% end to end, each of the values between turning points will correlate 100%, and the slopes will all have the same direction and rate. It should literally be a perfect match. The problem is that the calculated value was supposed to be MSST, and as such this is a poor result because each and every point is off by 0.5. So the multipliers in this case did not accurately calculate

CSST using the $X * \text{NMDP}^\circ\text{C} + Y * \text{CO}_2^\circ\text{C} + Z * \text{Slrr}^\circ\text{C} = \text{CSST}$ equation. This is critical since we want to know what percent our values do not form a perfect solution.

To test for this offset error, the sum of the point by point differences between CSST and MSST is divided by the mean value of MSST. The absolute value of this error is then subtracted from 1 to convert to a percent correct factor.

$$\%C = 1 - \left| \frac{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (y_i - x_i)}{M_x} \right| \quad (11)$$

Where:

$\%C$ = % Correct

x_i = Measured MSST value at point i

y_i = Calculated CSST value at point i

M_x = Mean of MSST.

Graph 2 Error Capture

Criterion 5 calculations

The final criterion is that the energy sources are not in and of themselves able to add energy evenly to the entire ocean surface in a short period of time because of the extreme volume of water involved, evaporation, mixing of the water due to waves and currents, location of the source, etc. To meet this criterion, all solutions with a 0 year offset are disregarded unless they have an almost perfect score on all 4 of the other criteria.

The exception to the must have an offset criterion is because this model is attempting to determine a proper result even if some of the assumptions are wrong. And if all 4 of the other criteria are the best solution then it can logically be assumed that this criterion would be wrong.

Calculating the best solution

The possible solutions to this problem consider that the offset for NMDP, CO_2 , or Slrr could be between 0 and 5 years. Anything beyond 5 years was considered excessive. In addition, each of the predictors could be responsible for 0% to 100% of the heat with CO_2 limited by the expected feedback for a doubling of CO_2 .

A computer program was written and tested to calculate all the aforementioned calculations. It can perform 2 types of operations.

First – It can loop through a cycle of varying the following:

NMDP year offset from 0 to -5 in increments of -1.

Slrr year offset with values 0 to -5 in increments of -1.

CO_2 year offset with values 0 to -5 in increments of -1.

NMDP Multiplier is changed from 0 to 1 in increments of 0.01.

Slrr Multiplier will be $1 - \text{NMDP Multiplier}$. Overall finer resolution in the percentages can be obtained by letting the Slrr and NMDP multipliers be independent but that amount of accuracy goes beyond the accuracy of the data

itself.

CO₂ Multiplier is changed from 0 to 1 in increments of 0.05.

This gives us 436,320 possible solutions. Results recorded for each possibility are:

NMDP Offset, CO₂ Offset, Slrr Offset, NMDP Multiplier, CO₂ Multiplier, Slrr Multiplier, End to End Correlation, Timed Correlation, % Calculated Values Correct, the product of the last three, and the number of slopes which are reversed.

Those results are then parsed and the largest of the product of the last three is determined as the solution while manually ensuring that the solution does not have a reversed slope and all three components have an offset.

Second – It can produce a csv file of all the calculation results for a single calculation pass where values for NMDP Multiplier, °C Temp rise for a Doubling of CO₂, NMDP Offset, CO₂ Offset, and Slrr Offset are manually entered. This will then allow the plotting of graphs for visual verification.

This second procedure will also sum all the NMDP, CO₂, and Slrr °C values independently as well as the sum of those three to calculate the % heat supplied by each component using the equations:

$$\%NMDPH = \frac{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (NMDP_i \text{ } ^\circ C)}{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (NMDP_i \text{ } ^\circ C + CO_{2i} \text{ } ^\circ C + Slrr_i \text{ } ^\circ C)} \quad (12)$$

$$\%CO_2H = \frac{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (CO_2 \text{ } ^\circ C)}{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (NMDP_i \text{ } ^\circ C + CO_{2i} \text{ } ^\circ C + Slrr_i \text{ } ^\circ C)} \quad (13)$$

and

$$\%SlrrH = \frac{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (Slrr \text{ } ^\circ C)}{\sum_{i=1880}^{1975} (NMDP_i \text{ } ^\circ C + CO_{2i} \text{ } ^\circ C + Slrr_i \text{ } ^\circ C)} \quad (14)$$

These values are the % of CSST heat.

CO₂ Degrees Rise and CO₂ Multiplier

As previously mentioned, in all calculations the CO₂°C to be added to get CSST is not based on a value normalized to the MSST value. It is a totally independent variable.

For the Full Run case the CO₂ Multiple is used to convert the CO₂°C from the entered °C for a doubling to a lower °C for a doubling since the function of these runs is to show possible solutions and not to solve for a single final solution.

Since the Full Run program only records the multiplier, the °C for a doubling entered at the start of the program (2°C) must be multiplied by the Multiplier to derive the °C for a doubling.

After several runs of the Full Run type it became obvious that 1°C for a doubling of CO₂ was too low because the readings were all best at the top end, and 4°C was too high as all peak values occurred with a multiple of 0.35 to 0.04 indicating accuracy was being sacrificed. The final runs were made with 2°C rise that produced peak results with multipliers very consistently at 0.75 which equates to 1.5°C for a doubling of CO₂.

Present Model Comparison

A second version of the program was cloned with the exception it holds the NMDP offset at 0 and the NMDP multiplier at 0 for a Full Run. This then produces a reduced set of data with the identical characteristics as the main program.

A full run to determine the characteristics of the presently accepted model was run on this second program.

Software and Data Sets

The calculations and methods in this section are done in 4 programs. The program to calculate all parameters under all conditions,

8075DegRise_CO2NMDPSIRR_V5_1.bas[10]. The program to select the best solution from the all conditions program 8075DegRise_SelectLargest.bas [11]. The program to calculate parameters without NMDP input 8075DegRise_NoNMDP_V1.bas[12]. The program to select the best solution from the no NMDP program output 8075DegRise_SelectLargestCO2Irrbas13.bas[13]. Calculation verification and graph generation (Version 5.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo[14]. Data For Calculating 1880 to 1975 sea surface temperature (Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo[15].

Results

Present Model

With no NMDP the only solution with no reversed slopes had 0 CO₂ and 0 Slrr offsets, its % Variables Correct was only 3.2%, its CO₂ multiplier was only 0.05 (0.10°C rise for doubling CO₂ vs 1.5+°C as per the IPCC Model[16]), and its Slrr multiplier was 0.02 (2%) which is physically impossible considering the expected value of Slrr and CO₂ alone should have been on the order of 10's of % so that solution was eliminated.

The best solution with no NMDP with a reversed slope was:

End to End Correlation =	68.39%
Timed Correlation =	46.41%
% Variables Correct =	95.05%
Product of previous 3=	30.17%
Reversed Slopes =	1
Number of 0 Offsets =	0
1880 - 1894 Corr. =	74.35%
1895 - 1911 Corr. =	73.48%
1912 - 1944 Corr. =	63.36%
1945 - 1975 Corr. =	0%
NMDP Offset =	NA
Slrr Offset =	-4 yr
CO ₂ Offset =	-3 yr

Graphically these values are presented in the following Graph 3 and Graph 4.

The Timed Correlation in this case was not considered valid with the reversed slope, so the End to End Correlation squared was used for r² which gives us a 47% coefficient of determination.

New Model

Using all three parameters the best solution was:

End to End Correlation =	87.77%
Timed Correlation =	89.26%
% Variables Correct =	99.99+%
Product of previous 3 =	78.35%
Reversed Slopes =	0
Number of 0 Offsets =	0
1880 - 1894 Corr. =	75.95%
1895 - 1911 Corr. =	88.27%
1912 - 1944 Corr. =	93.43%
1945 - 1975 Corr. =	91.82%
NMDP Offset =	-4 yr
Slrr Offset =	-3 yr
CO ₂ Offset =	-1 yr

The Timed Correlation then gives us an r² coefficient of determination of 79.61% [≈80 %].

Graphically these values are presented in the following Graph 5 and Graph 6, followed by Graph 7 which shows each source's contribution to the total.

Peer Reviewed - Awaiting Publication

Conclusion

With a 47% coefficient of determination we cannot say that the presently accepted model using only CO₂ and SIrr is a strong physical model. This fact combined with the mirrored slopes after 1945, which violate the fundamental principles of thermodynamics, also shows a not strong model.

With an 80% coefficient of determination we can say that the new model using CO₂, SIrr, and HGFA is a strong physical model. This fact combined with all the as calculated values slopes following the as measured slopes also shows a strong model.

This disparity in the coefficient of determination from 47% in the presently accepted model versus 80% in the new model combined with the fact that the new model does not violate the laws of thermodynamics shows that the presently accepted model is not as accurate as the new model.

The new model predicts a 1.5 °C temperature rise per doubling of CO₂. The presently accepted model assumes [16] a nominal 3.25°C rise for a doubling of CO₂ with a range from 1.5°C to 4.5°C. This would indicate that the presently accepted model and the new model both agree that the expected temperature rise for a doubling of CO₂ will be in the 1.5 °C range.

The new model would indicate that 51% of our energy increase was due to the HGFA heat addition to the oceans and its affect on the condensables, 30% was from increased CO₂ and its affect on the condensables, and 19% was from SIrr and its affects on condensables; indicating that CO₂ is neither the lone nor the primary temperature driver at the present conditions of our climate.

In addition we can say that there is a distinct possibility that the effect of HGFA is non linear and will require direct measurement of the heat added to the oceans and how that heat reflects to a change in surface sea temperature to determine its full effect and characteristics.

The new model also met the criteria that all three parameters have a delay associated with and they do. No conclusions can be drawn about the exact cause of these delays as there were no attempts to determine the probability of each thing that could cause the delay.

In conclusion we can say that the new model provides a solution in which the calculated temperatures are much more accurate and follow the laws of thermodynamics with finer granularity and overall accuracy.

Acknowledgment

This research was independently conducted, and was not funded by any corporation, government agency, or non-profit organization. The author is retired and has no working relationships with any educational institution, governmental body, or political party. All data and programs used in this research are referenced in the references section. All data and programs are accessible as either public governmental data or available through a Creative Commons Attribution license.

References

- 1 Williams B. (2016) The Correlation of North Magnetic Dip Pole Motion and Seismic Activity J Geol Geophys 2016, 5:6 DOI: 10.4172/2381-8719.1000262
- 2 Viterito A (2016) The Correlation of Seismic Activity and Recent Global Warming. J Earth Sci Clim Change. 7: 345. doi:10.4172/2157-7617.1000345
- 3 NASA Public Domain policy.
<https://pmm.nasa.gov/image-use-policy>
- 4 Andrew Lacis CO₂: The Thermostat that Controls Earth's Temperature (2010)
https://www.giss.nasa.gov/research/briefs/lacis_01/
- 5 NOAA NP.xy (30 Jan, 2015)
<http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/data/poles/NP.xy>
- 6 Met Office (2018)
[https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadsst3/data/HadSST.3.1.1.0/](https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadsst3/data/HadSST.3.1.1.0/diagnostics/HadSST.3.1.1.0_annual_globe_ts.txt)
- 7 Sato, Makiko, & Schmidt, Gavin (26 Jun, 2018)
<https://data.giss.nasa.gov/modelforce/ghgases/Fig1A.ext.txt>
- 8 NOAA, 2017
ftp://aftp.cmdl.noaa.gov/products/trends/co2/co2_mm_mlo.txt
- 9 Kopp, Greg (02 May, 2018)
http://spot.colorado.edu/~kopp/TSI/TIM_TSI_Reconstruction.txt
- 10 Williams, Bruce (16 Sep, 2018). Calculating sea surface temperature with north magnetic dip pole motion, CO₂, and solar irradiation. (Version 5.1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419654>
- 11 Williams, Bruce (15 Sep, 2018). Select best results from 3 source sea surface temperature calculations (Version 1.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419634>
- 12 Williams, Bruce. (15 Sep, 2018). Calculating sea surface temperature with CO₂ and solar irradiation (Version 1.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419629>
- 13 Williams, Bruce. (15 Sep, 2018). Select best results from 2 source sea surface temperature calculations (Version 1.0.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419638>
- 14 Williams, Bruce. (15 Sep, 2018). Calculation verification and graph generation (Version 5.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419640>
- 15 Williams, Bruce. (15 Sep, 2018). Data For Calculating 1880 to 1975 sea surface temperature (Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1419642>
- 16 Lindsey, Rebecca (24 Jan, 2014) How much will Earth warm if carbon dioxide doubles pre-industrial levels? <https://www.climate.gov/news-features/climate-qa/how-much-will-earth-warm-if-carbon-dioxide-doubles-pre-industrial-levels>

Peer Reviewed - Awaiting Publication

Old Model

New Model

Using Slrr and CO2 - Values

Graph 3 MSST and CSST Deviations from 0

Using Slrr and CO2 and NMDP - Values

Graph 5 MSST and CSST Deviations from 0

Using Slrr and CO2 - Linear Trend Line Comparison

Graph 4 MSST and CSST Linear Regression Lines

Using CO2 and Slrr and NMDP - Linear Trend Line Comparison

Graph 6 MSST and CSST Linear Regression Lines

Using Slrr and CO2 and NMDP - Individual Contributions

Graph 7 Slrr, CO2, and NMDP Individual Contributions